

CHANGES IN THE ACTIVITY OF LIVER-SPECIFIC ENZYMES IN EXPERIMENTAL HEPATITIS

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Abstract. *The problem of hepatitis is relevant all over the world. This disease has been tormenting all of humanity for many years. Therefore, the studies of the mechanisms of the disease are devoted to the works of many biochemists. In this work, changes in the activity of carbohydrate metabolism enzymes were studied: the liver-specific enzyme fructose-1-phosphate aldolase (F-1FA) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) in experimental hepatitis. The article examines changes in the activity of these enzymes and analyzes the mechanisms of these changes.*

Keywords: *hepatocytes, xenobiotics, fructose-1-phosphate aldolase enzyme, heliotrin.*

Аннотация. *Проблема гепатитов является актуальной во всем мире. Это заболевание в течении многих лет мучает все человечество. Поэтому изучению механизмов протекания посвящены труды многих биохимиков. В данной работе были изучены изменения активности ферментов углеводного обмена: печеночно-специфического фермента фруктозо-1-фосфат альдолазы (Ф-1ФА) и лактатдегидрогеназы (ЛДГ) при экспериментальном гепатите. В статье рассмотрены изменения в активности данных ферментов и разобраны механизмы данных изменений.*

Ключевые слова: *гепатоциты, ксенобиотики, фермента фруктозо-1-фосфат альдолаза, гелиотрин.*

An increase in LPO during heliotrin poisoning can serve as a factor destabilizing mitochondrial, cytoplasmic, lysosomal and other cellular membranes (I.G. Savin et al. 1981).

The first evidence of the disruption of the integrity of the cytoplasmic membranes during xenobiotic intoxication was an increase in the activity of cytoplasmic enzymes (F-1-FA, LDH, ALT, AST) in the blood serum. Increased permeability of cytoplasmic membranes leads to disruption, first of all, of carbohydrate metabolism and transamination of amino acids, since glycolysis and its provision with individual substrates is carried out by cytosol enzymes.

Carbohydrates are of exceptional importance as an energy material for the synthesis of various phosphorus-containing macroergic compounds that ensure the processes of biosynthesis of all components of cells and nucleic acids. The metabolism of carbohydrates is closely intertwined with the metabolism of nucleic acids, proteins and fats. In case of intoxication with hepatotropic xenobiotics, the processes of synthesis of glucose and its esters from lactic and pyruvic acids are inhibited [1,5]. To cover the body's energy needs (ATP) in case of glycolysis disorder, the hexose monophosphate pathway is included in the process, i.e. direct oxidation of glucose (pentose phosphate pathway).

One of the intermediate products of the pentose pathway, fructose-6-phosphate, is included in glycolysis under the action of the liver-specific enzyme fructose-1-phosphate aldolase (F-1-FA, EC. 4.1.2.7). When the liver is depleted of glycogen, the glycolysis process can be maintained by converting fructose-1-phosphate. Therefore, the activity of these enzymes is of great importance in studying carbohydrate metabolism. A number of authors noted that the

degree of increase in enzyme activity was directly dependent on the course of the pathological process and the severity of xenobiotic poisoning in experimental animals.

In this regard, to determine the degree of permeability of cell membranes and the state of carbohydrate metabolism, we studied the activity of F-1-FA in the liver and blood serum. The results of these studies are presented in Table 1

Table 1.
Indicators of F-1-FA activity (U/h tissue influ.) in the organs of rats treated with heliotrin (M + m) n = 8-10

Organs under study	Control	Days of research	
		50th	70th
Liver	86.5 ± 4.3	30.5 ± 0.9	22.5 ± 1.3
Blood serum	58.8 ± 2.94	500.1 ± 51.6*	430.0 ± 45.0*

Note: *p <0.05-0.001 calculated compared to control.

As can be seen from the table, when the xenobiotic is administered to experimental animals, a decrease in F-1-FA activity is observed in the liver and a significant increase in the blood serum. Identical changes are also observed on the 70th day of the experiment. Thus, in the liver of rats receiving heliotrin, on the 50th day, the activity of F-1-FA in the liver decreases by 2.83 times, and on the 70th day by 3.84 times. In the blood serum, the activity of this enzyme increased by 8.5 times on the 50th day and by 7.3 times on the 70th day.

The next, very important for the body, pathway of carbohydrate transformation is the pathway of transformation of trioses (pyruvic and lactic acids). Reversible transformation of lactic acid into pyruvic acid (PLA) is catalyzed by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) - lactate; NAD oxidoreductase (EC.1.1.1.27). It should be noted that in addition to glucose, PLA can also transform into a number of amino acids (ala, cis, tre, etc.), as well as glycerol. Consequently, this enzyme occupies a key place in the metabolic chain.

The results of studies by various authors indicate that intoxication with hepatotropic xenobiotics (CCl₄ , thioacetamide , heliotrin, etc.) causes accumulation of polypeptide chain reaction and lactic acid in the liver, increased activity of lactate dehydrogenase in the blood serum, and decreased level in the liver tissue [6]. However, no studies have been conducted to establish the relationship between changes in LDH activity and structural and functional changes in immunocompetent organs in toxic hepatitis. There is a lack of work on the relationship between the activity of these enzymes and the intensity of immune reactions.

Fig. 1. Changes in LDH activity in the dynamics of heliotrin poisoning

In animals given heliotrin (Fig. 1), a 1.3-fold decrease in LDH activity in the liver is observed on the 50th day, and these indicators continue to increase on the 70th day of the experiment. In parallel with the decrease in the activity of this enzyme in the liver, an increase in its activity in the blood serum is observed.

Analysis of the dynamics of changes in LDH activity in individual groups of animals receiving heliotrin revealed certain patterns that are important in understanding the mechanism of development of the pathological process and their relationship with the structure and function of PL and glycolipids.

An increase in the activity of this enzyme in the blood serum and a decrease in liver tissue is associated with an increase in the permeability of cytoplasmic membranes with subsequent disruption of gluconeogenesis from lactic acid.

Determination of the activity of this enzyme is of great importance in solving fundamental issues of carbohydrate metabolism and a general biological problem - the problem of hypoxia in the process of intoxication with xenobiotics.

All of the above on determining the activity of key glycolysis enzymes - F-1-FA, LDH - quite specifically reflects the biochemical changes occurring in the cytoplasm of hepatocytes of experimental animals. In the early period of the disease, the enzyme activity in the blood serum increases significantly, while in the liver their level decreases.

A study of the activity of F-1-FA and LDH showed that when rats are intoxicated with heliotrin, the indicated glycolytic enzymes undergo significant changes and lead to disruption of carbohydrate and energy metabolism, disruption of metabolism and the structural and functional state of membranes.

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